

Dark Matter Searches: Semi-visible Jets and Emerging Jets with Partial Event Building

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What is Dark Matter? Why have we not found it yet?

JORGE CHAM & DANIEL WHITESON
WHAT IS DARK MATTER?
 WEHAVENOIDEA.COM

A WHOPPING 27% OF THE UNIVERSE IS MADE OUT OF SOMETHING CALLED "DARK MATTER."

Stuff we know → 5%
 27% Dark Matter
 "Dark Energy"
 The Universe as we know it

BUT WHAT IS IT?

WE KNOW IT'S THERE BECAUSE IT KEEPS ALL THE STARS IN THE GALAXY FROM FLYING OFF.

AND BECAUSE IT BENDS LIGHT COMING FROM DISTANT GALAXIES.

BUT WE CAN'T SEE IT DIRECTLY. THE ONLY FORCE IT SEEMS TO FEEL IS GRAVITY.

- GRAVITY
- ELECTROMAGNETISM
- WEAK FORCE
- STRONG FORCE

THE AMAZING THING IS THAT WE DON'T KNOW WHAT IT COULD BE.

Are you it?

IT COULD BE A NEW KIND OF PARTICLE, OR A WHOLE NEW TYPE OF MATTER.

S'UP.

THERE MIGHT EVEN BE DARK MATTER SCIENTISTS OUT THERE WONDERING WHAT WE'RE MADE OF.

mono-X searches:
 X - SM object

... but what if we should look at unusual final states? 2

The Dark Sector: Semi-visible Jets (SVJ) and Emerging Jets (EJ)

What if there's not 1 DM particle but a whole sector of invisible particles that interact with each other?

If we produce a dark sector quark it will fragment and hadronize into dark sector hadrons which will then decay giving unusual topologies in our detector.

Different parameters, different jet phenomenologies. For example:

Semi-visible Jets (SVJ): produced when dark quarks decay partly to SM quarks and partly to stable dark hadrons (which are invisible) → missing transverse energy

Emerging Jets (EJ): dark hadrons undergoing displaced decays → displaced objects

! challenging event signature

displaced vertex: charged tracks originating from a displaced point
 r_{inv} : rate of stable dark hadrons / total dark hadrons

Properties of the SVJ signal

Lead jet pt (transverse momentum of leading jet in pT): momentum of most transversely energetic jet

MET (missing transverse momentum): event momentum imbalance in x-y plane

- ↑ high pT jets
- ↓ lower mediator masses peak from s-channel resonance
- ↓ higher mediator masses dominated by t-channel production
- ↑ high MET

Plotting the **lead jet pT** and the **MET** in the event:

515618	2000	4
515624	2500	4
515631	3000	6

r_inv: rate of stable dark hadrons / total dark hadrons

mediator mass: the mass of the ϕ in the production diagram

Triggers

How do we choose interesting events that we want to keep and study? We use triggers!

- Collisions in the LHC happen every 25 ns → 40 MHz rate of collisions → impossible to read-out or record data at that rate in ATLAS
- **Trigger** selects which events we want to keep for analysis → based on having high transverse momentum objects (e.g. jets, electrons, muons, etc.)
- Rate of data recorded needs to be shared between the different physics objects
- We record all events with high pT jets and also events with high MET
- But our signals have both of these properties - which trigger is best to record the most data?
- 💡 Look at efficiency of recording the data using different triggers

Semi-visible jets - trigger choice

What are the current triggers in ATLAS?

- ATLAS records all events satisfying any of:
 - **J420 trigger** → $r=0.4$ (small-R) jet w/ offline $p_T > 450$ GeV
 - **lcw_j460 trigger** → $r=1.0$ (large-R) jet w/ offline $p_T > 500$ GeV
 - **MET trigger** → offline $MET > 200$ GeV
- All 3 triggers:
 - ✓ record highest HT energy events
 - ✗ miss low HT signal
- 💡 Find highest efficiency by computing integrals of the plots

Signal 1: $r_{inv} = 0.4$, mediator mass = 2000 GeV

HT: scalar jet pt sum, hadronic transverse energy
incl: inclusive with 2-jet pre-selection, no triggers applied yet

Trigger Efficiencies for SVJ Signals

How much is each trigger capturing?

	small		
event/signal	515618	515624	515631
mediator mass	2000	2500	3000
r_inv	4	4	6
efficiency_J420	84.73%	62.56%	44.22%
efficiency_MET	70.86%	56.12%	49.85%
	large		
efficiency_lcw_j460	91.00%	79.00%	66.50%

- Current ATLAS analysis: uses MET trigger (met > 200 GeV) (simplest to use)
- But we see that slightly more signal events are recorded by the large-R trigger (r=1.0)
- For Run 3 analysis, we can revisit this strategy to recover some signal efficiency!
- I have also studied the efficiencies for emerging jet signals (internal)

Partial Event Building

Triggers can only do so much... so how can we save more events?

 We record only ~1-2 kHz of full ATLAS events \Rightarrow split between trigger signatures

 Possibility of recording more events if we record only PART of the detector and trigger information!

 Partial Event Building principle

 Find efficient triggers \Rightarrow more signal events than existing triggers

 Record enough information to distinguish them from background

Emerging jets appear displaced in the detector \Rightarrow Recording these ✨special ✨ jets \Rightarrow Separate new physics from SM jets

 Study what triggers for dark sector signals + retain enough information to distinguish against QCD

Feasibility Check of Partial Event Building

$$chf = \frac{\sum pT_{PV}^{trk}}{jetpT}$$

PEB for the dark sector is brand new... feasibility check first!

- Record information in region(s) around leading jet(s) with Partial Event Building → check that these contain “special” jets
- **charged fraction (chf)** - fraction of pT of the lead jet carried by primary vertex (PV) tracks (trk)
- Plot leading jet charged fraction

this looks like normal QCD jets with peak around 60%

we see lack of tracks (~0 chf) showing ✨ special ✨ nature of EJ

Next step for the project: Emulate whole PEB selection

New Trigger Choice for SVJ and EJ

- New triggers tried:
 - **allHT trigger** → scalar jet pt sum > 1000 GeV
 - **allHT650 trigger** → scalar jet pt sum > 650 GeV
- allHT650 trigger:
 - ✓ records highest HT energy events for both SVJ and EJ

SVJ Signal 1: $r_{\text{inv}} = 0.4$, mediator mass = 2000 GeV

EJ Signal 2: mediator mass = 1500 GeV, lifetime 10 mm

New Trigger Efficiencies for SVJ and EJ Signals

With allHT and allHT650

	Semi-visible Jet Signals		
event/signal	515618	515624	515631
mediator mass	2000	2500	3000
r_inv	4	4	6
efficiency_J420	84.73%	62.56%	44.22%
efficiency_MET	70.86%	56.12%	49.85%
efficiency_lcw_j460	83.03%	61.04%	42.01%
efficiency_allHT	84.14%	61.56%	40.65%
efficiency_allHT650	88.64%	67.89%	48.03%
Comparison vs allHT650			
allHT650 and J420	4.42%	7.86%	7.93%
allHT650 and allHT	6.33%	10.09%	12.55%

	Emerging Jet Signals		
event/signal	801925	801928	801932
dark confinement scale (λ_{dark})	1.6	1.6	40
Z prime mass [GeV]	600	1500	600
Dark pion mass [GeV]	0.8	0.8	20
Dark rho mass [GeV]	3.2	3.2	80
Lifetime [mm]	1	10	50
efficiency_J420	1.03%	58.19%	1.89%
efficiency_MET	0.00%	13.77%	0.81%
efficiency_lcw_j460	0.57%	46.68%	1.25%
efficiency_allHT	1.37%	49.38%	1.87%
efficiency_allHT650	10.56%	84.69%	8.79%
Comparison vs allHT650			
allHT650 and J420	90.28%	31.30%	78.49%
allHT650 and allHT	87.02%	41.69%	78.72%

How many regions of interest are required?

SVJ Signal 1: $r_{\text{inv}} = 0.4$, mediator mass = 2000 GeV

EJ Signal 2: mediator mass = 1500 GeV, lifetime 10 mm

How many regions of interest are required?

event/signal	801928
dark confinement scale (Λ_{dark})	1.6
Z prime mass [GeV]	1500
Dark pion mass [GeV]	0.8
Dark rho mass [GeV]	3.2
Lifetime [mm]	10
leadjet_2bins	44%
2ndjet_2bins	42%
3rdjet_2bins	20%
4thjet_2bins	3%
5thjet_2bins	0%

Charged fraction of first 5 jets for EJ signal 2 (Z' mass = 1500 GeV, lifetime = 10 mm)

Conclusion

- Semi-visible jet signals → high jet p_T and high MET

- Emerging jet signals → no tracks reconstructed from PV, particles produced are displaced from hard scatter

- Triggering on SVJ: large-R triggers perform well, allHT650 performs best

- Partial Event Building: promising way of increasing signal that we can record

- For PEB, 3rd jet has to be included to determine special nature of EJ signals

- Thanks to ATLAS, CERN, and CERN & Society!

